

IMPROVEMENT OF PASTURES AND THEIR PRODUCTIVITY CHARACTERISTICS IN KARAKOLUKH.

¹Khasan Tashpolat's son Javgashev

Graduate student of the department "Zooengineering and sericulture",
Tashkent branch of the Samarkand State University of Veterinary
Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology,

²Tursunbayeva Zuhra Rustam's daughter

Student of Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal
Husbandry and Biotechnology, Tashkent branch.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7336503>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 07th November 2022

Accepted: 15th November 2022

Online: 18th November 2022

KEY WORDS

Qorako'lichilik, texnologiya,
chorvachilik, naslchilik, fermer
xo'jaliklari, mahsuldorlik,
innovatsion texnologiya,
urg'ochi qo'y, chorva mollar,
yaylov, cho'pon, bioxilmaxillik.

ABSTRACT

Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimizda qorako'lichilik sohasining samarali yuritilishini, qorako'lichilikda yaylovlarni yaxshilash va ularning mahsuldorlik xususiyatlari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Inefficient and unsystematic use of pastures in the desert regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrease in pasture productivity, non-use of resource-saving technologies in livestock feeding, low level of development of the service and supply system for the livestock sector are negative for the biological diversity of the desert regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the main influencing factors. Further deepening of reforms in the field of cattle breeding, development of breeding limited liability companies (LLCs), personal assistants, farmers and farms engaged in pasture cattle breeding, ensuring their economically stable operation, financial support for the work of cattle herders in order to promote the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 28, 2019 "On measures to radically improve the state management system in

the field of veterinary and animal husbandry" No. PF-5696 [1], on March 14, 2018 "piracy on measures for the rapid development of the industry" No. PQ-3603 [2] and on August 16, 2019 "On measures for comprehensive development of the piracy network" No. 4420 [3] decisions were made.

As a result of the implemented institutional reforms, structural changes, production modernization measures, the volume of production in the livestock sector is growing relatively steadily. As a result of the reforms, the activities of 103 cattle-breeding joint-stock farms in Uzbekistan were restructured, and 36 of them were left as breeding limited liability companies. It is known that the effective management of the cattle-breeding sector depends first of all on scientifically based preservation of the breed of Karakol sheep and feeding

them with feed based on the ration, and on the basis of the introduction of innovative technologies and resource-saving developments in the management of the sector. focused activities are being implemented. In recent years, the main reason for the production and financial condition of farms specializing in pasture cattle breeding is ending in losses, and breeding works on farms, raising female sheep and rams separately, on a scientific basis. lack of flexibility, non-sustainability of measures to improve the biodiversity of pastures, and other such urgent issues. The results of the research showed that in cattle breeding, pastures should always be seasonally changed, that is, conditions should be created for natural regeneration of pastures, livestock should not be grazed in these areas for a while. The increase in the number of livestock is relatively stable and at a low rate under the management of the societies responsible for cattle breeding. However, the chronic grazing of unaccounted sheep of shepherds and other citizens on pastures together with the sheep of the limited liability company during the year causes non-observance of the system of grazing from pastures.

N.S. Gigineyshvili stated that "in Karakol sheep belonging to the desert type, the height of the legs should be considered as a positive product of natural selection, because in order to consume the required amount of feed, they rapidly travel large distances across the pasture high legs work. At the same time, it is necessary to consider the economy of covering the surface of the lake with strong, long, long cover of flowers as productive.

As a result of monographic observations, due to the fact that the population lives in the villages, the number of domestic jaidari,

relatively high-productivity livestock belonging to meat breeds is increasing. As a result, there is an increase in the size of degraded pasture lands around villages, wells and wells, the loss of existing desert forage plants, and the expansion of the number of harmful plants that are not eaten by sheep and cattle, and the areas occupied by them.

According to the results of our scientific observations, in many cases, local residents act in the manner of "the more the number of goods, the higher the income" in order to fully satisfy their family needs. As a result, they use pastures around villages for chronic livestock grazing without considering the productivity of available fodder plants. This situation ultimately causes an increase in the size of degraded areas in these pastures. In recent years, it has been demanded to introduce modern methods aimed at diversifying production in cattle breeding, ensuring product production in accordance with market requirements, and increasing the income of farms.

In the process of research, the factors influencing the activities of cattle breeding limited liability company and effective use of pastures were brought into a single system and described.

The set of factors influencing the activity of livestock farms and effective use of pastures is as follows:

Institutional factors:

pastoralism by relevant ministries and agencies at the regional level

non-implementation of coordinated planning and coordination activities in the management of the activities of its entities using stable mechanisms;

- lack of development of short-term and long-term development programs in

district administrations and farms specializing in pasture cattle breeding;

- non-compliance with local state bodies, cattle breeding limited liability company, ecosystem protection, prevention of desertification and other applicable legal requirements in economic entities specializing in cattle breeding;
- lack of financial opportunities for the development of the cattle breeding network in local self-governing bodies, livestock breeding limited liability company branch ministries and offices;

- shortage of working capital, low efficiency of use of natural resources. Social, cultural and economic factors:

- the socio-economic development measures of the pastoral areas are behind compared to other areas;
- limitation of opportunities to establish new permanent workplaces in pasture livestock areas;
- low level of attractiveness of attracting innovative developments and investments to the pasture livestock industry.

References:

1. Decree No. PF-5696 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 28, 2019 "On measures to radically improve the state management system in the field of veterinary and animal husbandry". <http://lex.uz>
2. Resolution PQ-3603 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 14, 2018 "On measures for rapid development of the piracy sector". <http://lex.uz>
3. Resolution No. 4420 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 16, 2019 "on measures for the comprehensive development of the piracy network". <http://lex.uz>
4. Project report in cooperation with UNDP, GEJ and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 2008, 31 pages.
5. Ergashev R. Kh., Ravshanov A. D. Innovative direction of sustainable development of the agrarian sector in Uzbekistan. - 2016. <http://eztuir.ztu.edu.ua/bitstream/handle/123456789/6004/325.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>